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Innovative expenditure tracking system aligned with ESG score

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ABSTRACT

This investigation presents a novel framework that combines product ESG scores and transportation ESG scores with customer purchasing behaviour for Sustainable Value Creation in the prepaid card and corporate spend management sectors. When we look at the classical customer purchase analysis behaviours, we can see behavioural targeting, for example, if the customer has looked at shoes, recommend similar shoes immediately, and RFM analysis to measure the long-term value of the customer, to establish a loyalty strategy, for example, a campaign to win back the customer who spends a lot but no longer shops. In the proposed system, unlike the existing literature, the mathematical model and infrastructure of an innovative expenditure tracking system are presented to instil sustainability awareness in both customers and businesses, thereby reducing environmental impacts.

1 INTRODUCTION

The review of existing literature highlights several methodological shortcomings in prior studies of customer value. Although the classic RFM model is valued for its ease of use and clear interpretability, it falls short in addressing the nuanced and evolving nature of contemporary consumer behaviour. Its simplistic structure limits its effectiveness in modelling the multifaceted dynamics of modern customer interactions and decision-making processes [1]. Although useful for initial customer classification, such approaches lack the predictive depth needed to accurately anticipate future customer actions, thereby restricting their real-world effectiveness in dynamic retail settings [2]. Such challenges are most apparent in retail environments that span multiple channels, where traditional RFM frameworks struggle to reflect the nuanced nature of customer activity [3]. Unlike the existing literature focused on behavioural targeting and traditional RFM, the proposed model provides the infrastructure for an innovative spend-tracking system to instill sustainability awareness in both customers and businesses, thereby reducing environmental impacts.

As a theoretical contribution, this study advances digital customer value research by combining classic segmentation models with ESG scoring, thereby enhancing the understanding of digital customer value. In practical terms, it provides e-commerce businesses with actionable tools to improve targeting, customer retention, and overall digital CRM performance. The study's organization is outlined below. Section 2 presents relevant scholarly work, while Section 3 describes the methodological framework employed in this investigation. Detailing the data collection process, pre-processing steps, and model construction, Section 4 elaborates on the main analytical insights, and Section 5 wraps up the paper with concluding observations.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

This study provides a timely and practical contribution to the field of sustainability-focused digital decision support systems. In particular, integrating ESG and RFM scores with campaign-based individual optimization is an essential step for data-driven marketing strategies. The article proposes an innovative system that incorporates ESG-based sustainability indicators with RFM-based customer analytics. Additionally, unlike the literature, the proposed study presents a pioneering system that promotes sustainable consumption. In this context, the literature review is presented under two headings, RFM and ESG score applications, in sections 2.1 and 2.2.

While RFM and ESG scoring systems have been studied extensively as separate frameworks, their combined application for advancing both marketing effectiveness and sustainability objectives remains a significant gap in the literature. This study addresses this gap by exploring the integration of these two approaches.

2.1 RFM Applications

The RFM methodology has emerged as a foundational tool in CRM for evaluating customer value and facilitating segmentation strategies. It assesses consumer behavior through the timing of the latest purchase, purchase frequency, and total spending volume. Its effectiveness in sectors like retail and hospitality is well-established, with proven utility in refining CRM operations [4, 5].

Utilizing RFM metrics, enterprises gain the ability to segment their clientele based on value and design precise marketing actions [6]. Building on traditional applications, Rahim [7] enhanced RFM's capability by integrating it with machine learning algorithms. Their approach involved constructing a 13-dimensional feature set that fused RFM metrics with additional statistical indicators—such as average, median, and kurtosis—to forecast repurchase tendencies. They employed models to achieve strong classification accuracy and to validate the model's resilience.

Moreover, clustering based on RFM dimensions proved effective in forming distinct customer segments, enabling more refined targeting [8]. As noted by Li et al. [9], combining the RFM methodology with machine learning provides a robust framework for leveraging transactional datasets to drive operational gains in retail settings.

Examining the refinement and adoption of the RFM framework reveals its significant impact on customer segmentation strategies and valuation processes. Employing clustering algorithms on transactional data reveals meaningful patterns in customer behavior, paving the way for more personalized and effective marketing efforts [8]. These insights not only enhance customer engagement but also drive profitability. As analytical approaches continue to grow in sophistication and scope, the RFM methodology remains a relevant core framework for assessing customer value across various industry contexts.

Despite the proven effectiveness of RFM-based segmentation in enhancing marketing outcomes, its potential for fostering sustainability-oriented consumer behaviour remains largely unexplored. This highlights the need for innovative approaches that leverage RFM analytics within the context of sustainability objectives.

2.2 ESG Score Applications

The allocation of weights in our primary ESG indicator framework is grounded in multiple widely accepted conceptual models, which collectively justify the significance assigned to the components, supported by contemporary data-driven findings.

The weighting scheme used in our ESG evaluation is based on a range of established theoretical perspectives, providing a sound rationale for the emphasis placed on each factor, further strengthened by up-to-date empirical data. The 40% weight attributed to the primary ESG indicator aligns with fundamental sustainability measurement principles outlined in the current literature, which underscores the critical role of direct indicators, such as domestic material consumption, in assessing sustainable practices [10]. Another body of research confirms that resource usage footprints effectively reflect environmental impact, thereby justifying the greater weight given to direct sustainability components in integrated indices [11]. This rationale underpins our decision to prioritize the Primary ESG indicator, which mirrors the immediate effect of consumer choices on sustainability. Meanwhile, the equal 15% allocation for metrics concerning consumption patterns and category diversity is theoretically justified by progress in sustainability evaluation. Another research also highlights that scorecard effectively incorporates sustainability into performance evaluations by balancing environmental, social, and economic factors [12].

Recent empirical findings on social influence in eco-conscious consumer behaviour further validate the 30% emphasis placed on Strong influence relationships. Another investigation demonstrates that social networks have a significant impact on sustainable food purchasing decisions through normative norms, highlighting their greater influence compared to that of unfamiliar individuals [13]. As a result, we have increased the weight of socially derived product preferences, acknowledging their effectiveness in promoting sustainability-oriented behaviour. According to contemporary sustainability modelling practices, the 40-15-15-30 weight allocation aligns with the model's theoretical orientation by assigning greater value to primary environmental indicators within a strong sustainability paradigm. [14]. his method ensures the inclusion of behavioral metrics, such as purchasing habits and product category variety, while also enhancing the model's ability to forecast outcomes accurately. Our grading system, divided into equal intervals from A to E, is informed by recent consumer segmentation research. One study, for instance, identified seven distinct consumer categories based on survey data collected from 3,000 Spanish participants [15]. At the same time, Sarti et al. (2018) utilized k-means cluster analysis to classify three consumer groups. These insights support our targeted marketing segmentation strategy [16]. Finally, the metric measuring diversity in purchase categories evaluates how widely customers shop across 11 distinct product groups. This provides essential insight into multi-category buying habits, which have been linked to stronger customer retention and greater long-term value, as documented [17]. In retail environments focused on sustainability, greater category diversification is often associated with heightened environmental awareness, as consumers engage in sustainable practices across various domains, as noted [18]. This measure accounts for 15% of the total score, highlighting its significance both theoretically and empirically as a marker of dedication to sustainability.

Although ESG-based metrics provide a robust framework for evaluating sustainability at the consumer level, integrating these insights with advanced customer analytics such as RFM remains an underdeveloped area, this represents a significant opportunity for innovation in data-driven marketing, particularly in the context of promoting sustainable consumption.

3 MATERIALS AND METHOD

While both RFM and ESG scoring systems have demonstrated significant utility within their respective domains, their combined application presents a promising avenue for developing more holistic and practical digital decision-support systems. By aligning marketing strategies with sustainability objectives, this integrated approach addresses a critical gap in the literature and supports the transition towards more responsible and impactful business practices.

The steps of the proposed system are shown in detail in Figure 1.

3.1 Proposed System Framework

Figure 1: Proposed System Framework

Step 1-2: Data Preparation and Collection and Scoring

To build this model, you need to assign each customer a score (typically between 1–5 or 1–10) for each of the following components:

Step 3: RFM and ESG Scoring

1. RFM Score (Recency, Frequency, Monetary)

A classic metric for customer segmentation.

- Recency (R): Time since the customer's last purchase (more recent = higher score).
- Frequency (F): Number of total purchases (more frequent = higher score).
- Monetary (M): Total amount spent by the customer (higher spending = higher score).

How to calculate:

- Compute R, F, and M for each customer.

- Rank all customers for each metric and assign percentile-based scores (e.g., top 20% gets 5, next 20% gets 4, etc.).
- Combine them into a composite *RFMScore*:

$$RFMScore = (RxW_r) + (FxW_f) + (MxW_m) \quad (1)$$

2. Product ESG Score (P-ESG)

This evaluates each product's sustainability and social impact profile.

- Environmental (E): Material sources (e.g., recycled?), carbon footprint during production, water usage, packaging recyclability.
- Social (S): Fair trade certifications, local sourcing, supply chain transparency.
- Governance (G): Brand-level certifications and governance transparency (e.g., B Corp).

How to calculate:

- Score each product manually on a scale (e.g., 1–10) based on E, S, and G factors.
- For each customer, compute the average ESG score of purchased products:

$$P-ESG = (E+S+G)/3 \quad (2)$$

3. Logistics Sustainability Score (L-ESG)

Measures the environmental impact of the delivery process.

- Delivery Mode: Electric vehicle or bike (high score) vs. diesel or air cargo (low score).
- Distance: Proximity of customer to warehouse (closer = higher score).
- Packaging: Minimal, recyclable packaging (high score).
- Delivery Option: Green delivery (consolidated/eco-friendly) gets a higher score.

How to calculate:

- Score each order between 1–10 based on the above criteria.
- Compute each customer's average delivery sustainability score:

3.2 Mathematical Modelling

Several mathematical models have been developed in the literature, focusing on product marketing. For instance, Bigler et al. (2023) developed a framework to address large-scale customer assignment problems in direct marketing, incorporating realistic business constraints such as budgets, timing, communication frequency, and conflict constraints [19]. Their study demonstrated that analysing customer data through grouping and pre-processing techniques significantly improves decision quality and scalability compared to traditional optimization approaches. Similarly, the present study proposes an innovative expenditure tracking model that integrates product and transportation ESG scores with customer purchasing behaviour to strengthen sustainability awareness and support sustainable value creation.

Indexes:

i : Index representing customers ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N$)

j : Index representing campaigns ($j = 1, 2, \dots, K$)

Parameters :

RFM_i : The RFM score of customer i , normalized between 1–100. (*Represents economic potential*)

SC_i : The Sustainability Consciousness Score of customer i , normalized between 1–100. This combines the average Product ESG Score and the average Logistics ESG Score. (*Represents ecological potential*)

$Cost_j$: The cost of applying campaign j to a customer.

Eco_Impact_j : The ecological impact score (1–50 scale) of campaign j . For example, a "Green Delivery" campaign would have a high Eco Impact score, whereas a generic "10% Discount" campaign might have a score of zero.

$P_{i,j,k}$: The probability (in %) that customer i will respond positively (e.g., purchase, click) when campaign j about product k is offered. This is the most critical parameter and should be predicted from historical data using machine learning models (e.g., Logistic Regression).

B : Total marketing budget.

α : Weight assigned to economic value in the objective function (a coefficient between 0 and 1).

β : Weight assigned to sustainability value in the objective function (a coefficient between 0 and 1).

It must hold that $\alpha + \beta = 1$

Decision Variables (Model Outputs)

$X_{i,j,k}$: A binary decision variable.

Mathematical Model Formulation

Explanation of the objective Function:

The goal is to maximize the total expected value derived from assigning campaigns to customers. The explanation of the objective function (3) is given below in order.

$P_{i,j,k}$: the probability that customer i will respond positively to campaign j about product k (e.g., by clicking, purchasing, or engaging). A campaign can only create value if the customer responds to it. This probability acts as a weight on all other terms.

αRFM_i : Represents the *expected economic value* of assigning a campaign to customer i . Customers with higher RFM scores are more likely to generate revenue.

$(\beta SC_i + Eco_Impact_j)$: Represents the expected sustainability value of the assignment. It consists of:

SC_i : The customer's current level of sustainability awareness.

Eco_Impact_j : The ecological benefit offered by campaign j .

Combining these two allows us to prioritize both receptive customers and high-impact campaigns.

$X_{i,j,k}$: A binary decision variable that ensures this value is included only if campaign j about product k is actually assigned to customer i ($X_{i,j,k}=1$). If no campaign is assigned, the value contributed is zero.

$$\text{Maximize } Z = \sum_i \sum_j \sum_k [P_{i,j,k} (\alpha \text{ RFM}_i + \beta (\text{SC}_i + \text{Eco_Impact}_j))] X_{i,j,k} \quad (3)$$

Constraints:

Budget constraint (4): The total cost of all assigned campaigns must not exceed the overall marketing budget. This ensures that the campaign assignments stay within the available financial resources.

$$\sum_i \sum_j \sum_k (\text{Cost}_j X_{i,j,k}) \leq B \quad (4)$$

Stock constraint (5): This constraint ensures that the total quantity of product k assigned across all customers and all campaigns does not exceed the current stock level of that product. In other words, it sets a limit to ensure that the campaign assignments do not exceed the product supplies.

$$\sum_i \sum_j X_{i,j,k} \leq \text{Stock}_k \quad (5)$$

The customer’s current level of sustainability awareness constraint (6)

$$\text{SC}_i \geq \frac{\text{SC}_i - \text{MinSC}_i}{\text{MaxSC}_i - \text{MinSC}_i} \quad (6)$$

Assignment constraint (5): Each customer can receive at most one campaign. This prevents campaign fatigue and over-targeting.

$$\sum_j X_{i,j,k} \leq 1 \quad \forall i \quad (7)$$

This guarantees that no customer is overwhelmed with multiple offers simultaneously.

Binary Variable constraint (6): Decision variables are binary — a campaign is either assigned to a customer or not.

$$X_{i,j,k} \in \{0,1\} \quad \forall i, j, k \quad (8)$$

$X_{i,j,k}=1$ if campaign j is assigned to customer i ; otherwise, it is 0.

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This study presents a sustainable consumption model within the scope of sustainability-focused digital decision support systems. In particular, integrating ESG and RFM scores with campaign-based individual optimization is an essential step for data-driven digital marketing. The article proposes an innovative system that incorporates ESG-based sustainability indicators with RFM-based customer analytics. RFM analysis helps create more effective and targeted marketing strategies by segmenting customers based on criteria such as shopping frequency (Frequency), time since last purchase (Recency), and spending amount (Monetary). The details of how Recency and Frequency metrics are calculated are provided below.

Recency was measured using a five-point ordinal scale, with each level representing a specific time window:

- Level 1: Transactions recorded over a duration exceeding 365 days.
- Level 2: Transactions made throughout the 181–365 day interval.
- Level 3: Transactions during the 91–180 day timeframe.
- Level 4: Transactions completed in the 31–90 calendar day span.
- Level 5: Transactions within the most recent 30-day period.

Purchase frequency was similarly mapped onto a five-point scale, based on the interval between purchases:

- Level 1: More than 120 calendar days separating transactions.
- Level 2: 61 to 120 days elapsed from one transaction to the next.
- Level 3: 31 to 60 days gap between consecutive transactions.
- Level 4: 15 to 30 days interval among transactions.
- Level 5: Intervals shorter than 15 calendar days across transactions.

4.1 RFM Data and descriptive statistics

The proposed study was conducted in the Employee Benefit & Expense Management Solutions sector. The data used in the study belongs to a fintech company that provides corporate meals, fuel, gift cards & and payment system services in Turkey. There are 17 member businesses in this company, and the member businesses with the highest transaction rates — numbered 1, 3, 6, 8, 13, and 17 — were taken into consideration in the study. There are a total of 25,576 users in these member businesses. Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics of the RFM scores for these users.

Table 1: RFM metrics of the Total Unique Users: 25576

Metric	Mean	Median	Std. Dev	Skewness	Kurtosis
Recency	3.41	4.00	1.44	-0.41	-1.20
Frequency	1.00	1.00	0.05	46.58	2767.94
Monetary	1.00	1.00	0.06	31.35	1251.42
RFM Score	5.42	6.00	1.45	-0.37	-1.07

Table 1 shows that the Skewness and Kurtosis values for Frequency and Monetary are generally very high, indicating that the data distributions are highly skewed to the right and exhibit extreme values. Also, Recency and RFM Score are more symmetrical and closer to a normal distribution. As illustrated in Figure 2, the average RFM scores were calculated for 25,576 users associated with partner businesses 1, 3, 6, 8, 13, and 17. Among these, businesses 1 and 3 exhibit the highest RFM scores.

Figure 2: Average RFM scores for participating merchants numbered 1, 3, 6, 8, 13, and 17

Recent studies have emphasized the role of clustering algorithms in enhancing data-driven marketing analytics. John, Shobayo, and Ogunleye (2023) compared various clustering methods, including K-Means, GMM, DBSCAN, BIRCH, and agglomerative clustering for customer segmentation in the UK retail sector, identifying the Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) as the most effective based on its Silhouette Score performance [20]. Similarly, Gustriansyah, Suhandi, and Anthony (2020) enhanced RFM (Recency, Frequency, Monetary) analysis through an improved K-Means approach that integrates multiple validity indices to optimize cluster determination and segmentation accuracy [8]. Building on these data-driven segmentation approaches, the present study incorporates product and transportation ESG scores with customer purchasing behavior to propose a sustainability-oriented expenditure tracking model that supports sustainable value creation for both businesses and consumers. To determine the optimal number of clusters, the Elbow method was applied by plotting the within-cluster sum of squares (WCSS) against the number of clusters. The "elbow point" in Figure 3 indicated the appropriate number of clusters. According to the results shown in Table 2 and Figure 3, the cluster number is chosen as 4.

Figure 3: The optimal number of clusters was determined using the Elbow method.

Table 2: Index values of Silhouette and Calinski-Harabasz scores for different cluster numbers 25576 users

k	Silhouette	Calinski-Harabasz
2	0.5710	50278.92
3	0.4817	45540.64
4	0.5142	48732.92
5	0.4797	52803.11
6	0.4413	50971.43
7	0.4492	50144.17
8	0.4583	49994.15
9	0.4196	49818.60
10	0.3836	48695.27

Figure 4: The clustering analysis performed on all users resulted in four distinct clusters.

Preparation of parameters:

- RFM_i and SC_i scores are calculated for each customer from your CRM and sales data.
- The marketing department defines and scores each campaign.
- The most challenging part: Our data scientists estimate the probability for each customer-campaign pair by building a machine learning model based on past campaign results. The management determines the weights α and β , as well as the total budget B , according to the strategic objectives (e.g., $\alpha = 0.7$ in the profitability-oriented period, $\beta = 0.6$ in the sustainability campaign period). This mathematical formulation is an integer linear programming (ILP) problem. To solve it, we use the GAMS optimization program. The parameter values are given in Table 2. Also, 200 users and 20 campaigns are considered for each customer segment in member companies 1, 3, 6, 8, 13, and 17.

Table 2: The values of the experiment parameters

$P_{i,j}$	SC_i	Eco_Impact_j	α	β
0.7	0-10	1-10	0.5	0.5

The output of the model gives you a clear action plan, such as below:

- "Assign Campaign 3 ('Green Delivery' discount) to Customer 78." ($X_{78,3} = 1$)
- "Assign Campaign 1 ('15% Off New Season Sustainable Products') to Customer 105." ($X_{105,1} = 1$)
- "Do not assign any campaigns to customer 192." (All $X_{192,j}$'s for this customer are zero because the expected value of assigning a campaign to this customer is lower than its cost).

Instead of relying on intuition or simple segmentations, this model allows you to build a data-driven, optimized, and strategically flexible campaign management system. There are four different customer clusters. The objective function values according to the four RFM segments are calculated. These six sample sets of objective function values belong to 200 participating merchants numbered 1, 3, 6, 8, 13, and 17, with four different RFM segments shown in Figure 6. Also, the campaign rates are given in Figure 7.

Figure 6: Objective function values for different RFM segment customers

Figure 7: Campaign assignment rates for different RFM segment customers

5 FUTURE WORK

While this study introduces an integrated approach combining ESG-based sustainability indicators and RFM-based customer analytics for campaign-based individual optimization, several avenues for future research remain open.

First, future studies could explore the application of the proposed system across different industries and cultural contexts to assess its generalizability and adaptability. Since consumer behavior and sustainability priorities can vary significantly by sector and region, comparative studies would provide valuable insights into the model's robustness and scalability.

Second, integrating additional data sources, such as real-time behavioral data, social media activity, or psychographic variables, could further enhance the predictive power and personalization capabilities of the decision support system. Investigating the role of emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence and advanced machine learning algorithms, may also improve the accuracy and effectiveness of both ESG and RFM scoring mechanisms.

Third, future research could focus on the long-term impact of sustainability-oriented marketing strategies on consumer loyalty, brand equity, and overall business performance. Longitudinal studies would be instrumental in evaluating whether the integration of ESG and RFM analytics leads to sustained changes in consumer behavior and measurable improvements in environmental and social outcomes.

Fourth, ethical considerations and potential unintended consequences of data-driven segmentation and targeting should be examined. Ensuring transparency, fairness, and consumer privacy will remain crucial as digital decision support systems become more sophisticated.

Finally, collaboration with policymakers and industry stakeholders could facilitate the development of standardized frameworks and best practices for integrating sustainability metrics into customer analytics. Such efforts could accelerate the adoption of responsible marketing strategies and contribute to the broader goals of sustainable development.

By addressing these directions, future research can build on the foundations laid by this study, advancing both the theory and practice of sustainability-focused digital decision support systems.

6 CONCLUSION

This study contributes to the evolving field of sustainable consumption by proposing an integrative framework that aligns ESG-based product and transportation metrics with customer purchasing behaviours. By moving beyond conventional customer analytics such as behavioural targeting and RFM-based loyalty segmentation, the proposed model offers a data-driven and sustainability-oriented expenditure tracking system. This novel approach not only supports corporate sustainability goals but also promotes environmentally responsible consumption habits among customers. Ultimately, the framework provides a practical foundation for businesses in the prepaid card and corporate spend management sectors to embed sustainability into their core decision-making processes, thereby fostering long-term value creation for both organizations and society.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. A. Gomes and T. Meisen, "A review on customer segmentation methods for personalized customer targeting in e-commerce use cases," *Information Systems and e-Business Management*, vol. 21, no. 3, pp. 527–570, 2023.
- [2] H. Zare and S. Emadi, "Determination of customer satisfaction using improved K-means algorithm," *Soft Computing*, vol. 24, no. 22, pp. 16947–16965, 2020.
- [3] S. Kim, W. Shin, and H.-W. Kim, "Predicting online customer purchase: The integration of customer characteristics and browsing patterns," *Decision Support Systems*, vol. 177, Art. no. 114105, 2024.

- [4] M. M. D. Alam, R. A. Karim, and W. Habiba, "The relationship between CRM and customer loyalty: The moderating role of customer trust," *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, vol. 39, no. 7, pp. 1248–1272, 2021.
- [5] C. Ledro, A. Nosella, and A. Vinelli, "Artificial intelligence in customer relationship management: Literature review and future research directions," *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*, vol. 37, no. 13, pp. 48–63, 2022.
- [6] C. Rungruang, P. Riyapan, A. Intarasit, K. Chuarkham, and J. Muangprathub, "RFM model customer segmentation based on hierarchical approach using FCA," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 237, Art. no. 121449, 2024.
- [7] M. A. Rahim, M. Mushafiq, S. Khan, and Z. A. Arain, "RFM-based repurchase behavior for customer classification and segmentation," *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, vol. 61, Art. no. 102566, 2021.
- [8] R. Gustriansyah, N. Suhandi, and F. Antony, "Clustering optimization in RFM analysis based on k-means," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 470–477, 2020.
- [9] Y. Li, X. Chu, D. Tian, J. Feng, and W. Mu, "Customer segmentation using K-means clustering and the adaptive particle swarm optimization algorithm," *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 113, Art. no. 107924, 2021.
- [10] K. Mensah, C. Wieck, and B. Rudloff, "Sustainable food consumption and sustainable development goal 12: Conceptual challenges for monitoring and implementation," *Sustainable Development*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 1109–1119, 2024.
- [11] Z. J. Steinmann, A. M. Schipper, M. Hauck, S. Giljum, G. Wernet, and M. A. Huijbregts, "Resource footprints are good proxies of environmental damage," *Environmental Science & Technology*, vol. 51, no. 11, pp. 6360–6366, 2017.
- [12] C. Mio, A. Costantini, and S. Panfilo, "Performance measurement tools for sustainable business: A systematic literature review on the sustainability balanced scorecard use," *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 367–384, 2022.
- [13] I. Schubert, J. I. de Groot, and A. C. Newton, "Challenging the status quo through social influence: Changes in sustainable consumption through the influence of social networks," *Sustainability*, vol. 13, no. 10, Art. no. 5513, 2021.
- [14] N. Pollesch and V. H. Dale, "Applications of aggregation theory to sustainability assessment," *Ecological Economics*, vol. 114, pp. 117–127, 2015.
- [15] J.-L. Vázquez, A. Lanero, J. A. García, and X. Morano, "Segmentation of consumers based on awareness, attitudes and use of sustainability labels in the purchase of commonly used products," *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, vol. 38, pp. 115–129, 2023.
- [16] S. Sarti, N. Darnall, and F. Testa, "Market segmentation of consumers based on their actual sustainability and health-related purchases," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 192, pp. 270–280, 2018.
- [17] R. U. Khan, Y. Salamzadeh, Q. Iqbal, and S. Yang, "The impact of customer relationship management and company reputation on customer loyalty: The mediating role of customer satisfaction," *Journal of Relationship Marketing*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 1–26, 2022.
- [18] M. J. Muñoz-Torres, M. Fernández-Izquierdo, J. M. Rivera-Lirio, and E. Escrig-Olmedo, "Can environmental, social, and governance rating agencies favour business models that promote a more sustainable development?" *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 439–452, 2019.
- [19] T. Bigler, M. Kammermann, and P. Baumann, "A matheuristic for a customer assignment problem in direct marketing," *European Journal of Operational Research*, vol. 304, no. 2, pp. 689–708, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.ejor.2022.04.009.
- [20] J. M. John, O. Shobayo, and B. Ogunleye, "An exploration of clustering algorithms for customer segmentation in the UK retail market," *Analytics*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 809–823, 2023.